

ISOMORPHISMS OF LOG-ALGEBRAS

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Annation: Let (Ω, μ) be a σ -finite measure space, and let $L_0(\Omega, \mu)$ be the $*$ -algebra of all complex (real) valued measurable functions on (Ω, μ) . The $*$ -subalgebra

$L_{\log}(\Omega, \mu) = \left\{ f \in L_0(\Omega, \mu) : \int_{\Omega} \log(1 + |f|) d\mu < +\infty \right\}$ of $L_0(\Omega, \mu)$ is called the algebra of

log-integrable measurable functions on (Ω, μ) . Using the notion of passport of a normed Boolean algebra, we give the necessary and sufficient conditions for a $*$ -isomorphism of two algebras of log-integrable measurable function.

Keywords: Integrable function, space, passport of Boolean algebra, Isomorphism of log-algebras, log-integrable function

The study of L_p spaces was like Banach, who described the isometries of $L_p[0,1]$, $p \neq 2$ spaces. The products of this direction were given by Yedon, who described all their isometries in L_p dimensions in different dimensions.

We denote the set of $\nabla = \nabla_{\mu}$ -dimensional functions as $L_0(\nabla_{\mu}) = L_0(\Omega, A, \mu)$.

Algebra $L_0(\nabla_{\mu})$ was seen in the work "Space isometries of logarithm-integrable functions":

$$L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu}) = \left\{ f \in L_0(\nabla_{\mu}) : \|f\|_{\log} = \int_{\Omega} \log(1 + |f|) d\mu < +\infty \right\}$$

log-integrable dimensional functions and every $f \in L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$ for

$$\text{let's match } \|f\|_{\log} = \int_{\Omega} \log(1 + |f|) d\mu$$

$\|\cdot\|_{\log} : L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu}) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ functions are considered F-norm and satisfy the following conditions.

Explanation.

(i). $\|f\|_{\log} > 0$ all of $0 \neq f \in L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$;

(ii). $\|\alpha f\|_{\log, \mu} \leq \|f\|_{\log, \mu}$ any $f \in L_{\log}(\nabla, \mu)$ va $\alpha \leq 1$ numbers;

(iii). $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \|\alpha f\|_{\log, \mu} = 0$ all $f \in L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$ for;

(iv). $\|f + g\|_{\log, \mu} \leq \|f\|_{\log, \mu} + \|g\|_{\log, \mu}$ all of $f, g \in L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$ for.

Theorem.1. $L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$ and $L_{\log}(\nabla_{\nu})$ F-spaces should be only this equation $\mu(\Omega) = \nu(\Omega)$.

We say that μ and ν (Ω, A) on measurable spaces and $0 \leq \frac{d\nu}{d\mu} := h$ - Rodon-Nikodim's

derivative, $\nu(x) = \mu(hx)$. That is clear, space

$$L_{\log}(\nabla_{\nu}) = \left\{ f \in L_0(\nabla) : \int_{\Omega} \log(1+|f|)d\nu < +\infty \right\}$$

$$\left\{ f \in L_0(\nabla) : \int_{\Omega} h \cdot \log(1+|f|)d\mu < +\infty \right\} = L^{\nu}_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$$

and has the following norm

$$\|f\|_{\log, \nu} = \int_{\Omega} \log(1+|f|)d\nu = \int_{\Omega} h(\log(1+|f|))d\mu : \|f\|_{\log, \mu}^{\nu}$$

We also need the following analogue of the space of log-integrable dimensional functions:

$$L^{(\nu)}_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu}) = \left\{ f \in L_0(\nabla) : \int_{\Omega} \log(1+h|f|)d\mu < +\infty \right\} \quad \|f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)} = \int_{\Omega} \log(1+h|f|)d\mu$$

F-norm. This follows from the following.

Explanation.

$\|f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)}$ function satisfies the following conditions:

- (i). $\|f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)} > 0$ all of $0 \neq f \in L_{\log}(\nabla_{\mu})$;
- (ii). $\|\alpha f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)} \leq \|f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)}$ any for $f \in L_{\log}(\nabla, \mu)$ and $\alpha \leq 1$;
- (iii). $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \|\alpha f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)} = 0$ all of $f \in L_{\log}(\nabla, \mu)$ for ;
- (iv). $\|f + g\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)} \leq \|f\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)} + \|g\|_{\log, \mu}^{(\nu)}$ all $g, f \in L_{\log}(\nabla, \mu)$ for.

Let's remind,

$$L_p(\nabla) = \left\{ f \in L_0(\nabla) : \int_{\Omega} |f|^p d\mu < +\infty \right\}, \|f\|_{p, \mu} = \left(\int_{\Omega} |f|^p d\mu \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

$$L_p(\nabla_{\mu}) = \left\{ f \in L_0(\nabla) : \int_{\Omega} h|f|^p d\mu < +\infty \right\}$$

$$\|f\|_{p, \nu} = \left(\int_{\Omega} |f|^p d\nu \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \left(\int_{\Omega} (h|f|^p)d\mu \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

Therefore, in the equivalent cases μ and ν $U : L_p(\nabla_{\mu}) \rightarrow L_p(\nabla_{\nu})$ defined by the equation $U(f) = h^{-1}f$, $f \in L_p(\nabla_{\mu})$ the opposite is a linear surjective isometry from $L_p(\nabla_{\mu})$ to $L_p(\nabla_{\nu})$.

Description. $L_{\log}^{\nu}(\nabla \mu)$ is an external log-space and $L_{\log}^{(\nu)}(\nabla \mu)$ is an internal log-space is called. The space $L_{\log}^{(\nu)}(\nabla \mu)$ is not an algebra at all.

Description. Meras μ and ν are called α -equivalent, if on ∇

$$L_{\log}^{\nu}(\nabla \mu) = L_{\log}^{(\nu \cdot \alpha^{-1})}(\nabla \mu).$$

if there is an automorphism satisfying the equality.

Theorem. If $L_{\log}^{\nu}(\nabla \mu)$ is the algebra $L_{\log}(\nabla \mu)$ and $L_{\log}^{(\nu)}(\nabla \mu)$, it is necessary and sufficient for the algebras to be isomorphic that μ and ν are α -equivalent.

Theorem. If ∇ is homogeneous, $L_{\log}(\nabla \mu)$ and $L_{\log}^{(\nu)}(\nabla \mu)$ are finite in dimension, and the algebras are isomorphic.

References:

1. Dykema K., Sukochev F., Zanin D. Algebras of log-integrable functions and operators. // Journal Complex Anal. Oper. Theory 10, 8. 2016. –С. 1775–1787.
2. Segal I., A non-commutative extension of abstract integration. // Ann. of Math. 1953 –С. 401–457.
3. Трунов Н.В. К теории нормальных весов на алгебрах Неймана. // Изв. вузов. Матем., 1982, 8, –С. 61-70.
4. Трунов Н.В. L_p -пространства, ассоциированные с весом на полуконечных алгебрах фон Неймана. // Констр. Теор. Функ. Анал. 3, 1981. –С.88-93.

